

SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES: NANO-REINFORCEMENT AND MULTIFUNCTIONALIZATION

Haibao Lu, Jinsong Leng, Shanyi Du

¹Centre for Composite Materials, Harbin Institute of Technology
P.O. Box 3010, No. 2 Yikuang Street, Harbin 150080, China
Email: sydu@hit.edu.cn, web page: <http://homepage.hit.edu.cn/pages/dushanyi/1>

Keywords: Smart materials and structures, Shape memory polymer, Nanocomposite

ABSTRACT

Shape memory capability and tailorable properties enable shape memory polymer (SMP) with great potential applications in biomedicine, aerospace, electronic engineering, civil engineering and textiles. Similar to other types of polymer nanocomposites, mixing of SMP and nano-sized reinforcement has opened pathways for engineering flexible nanocomposites that exhibit novel mechanical, optical, electrical or magnetic properties, as well as functional or multifunctional performance. By incorporating functional nano-sized reinforcement, multifunctional SMP nanocomposites have further enhanced and broadened the wide applications in comparison with pristine SMPs. This paper reviews various functions of the SMP nanocomposites, focusing in research and development on mechanical reinforcement, actuation approaches and multifunctionalization. Various performances of these nanocomposites and the mechanisms behind experimental phenomena are summarized and discussed. Furthermore, the potential research directions and future progresses are also discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) have a capability of memorizing their original shape upon exposure to an external stimulus, such as thermal heating, light, electromagnetic resistive joule heating or chemicals [1-3]. The advantages of the SMPs over their traditional shape memory alloy (SMA) counterpart include low density, capabilities for high magnitude shape recovery, easy manufacture processes and tailorable properties to precisely meet the needs for particular applications [4-6]. Currently, SMP has become a very hot topic and gained widespread attentions around the world due to their exciting properties and performance. These unique characteristics enable SMPs to be used in a wide range of fields. However, with the application domains increasingly widening, some major limitations of SMPs still exist and impose great challenges to their broad utilizations [3,4,5]. Some of the key limitations include low mechanical stiffness and strength due to low rubbery moduli, long recovery time and slow response ability (tens of seconds in open air for the SMPs vs. tens of milliseconds for the SMAs) due to the low thermal conductivity, inertness to electromagnetic stimuli owing to their electromagnetic insulation of most polymeric materials [4,6,7]. To overcome these challenges, many current works have been focused on improving mechanical, electromagnetic and conductive properties by incorporation of various functional fillers into SMPs to achieve multifunctionalization [8-12].

There are many efforts aiming on enhancing the mechanical properties and recovery strength of the SMPs [8]. Nanocomposites have outstanding mechanical properties, such as high elastic stiffness and high strength, due to large ratios of surface area to volume for the nano-sized additives when compared to the micro- and macro-sized additives [9]. The advantages using nano-scale reinforcement rather than micro-scale ones include significant surface area improvement, larger polymer chain confinement, higher stiffness and tensile strength, higher tensile modulus and flexural strength [9]. Some nano-sized fillers, such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) or clays could provide nano-scaled zig-zag/tortuous diffusion path and large interfacial areas, leading to an enhanced barrier for thermal, gas or moisture penetration [10].

To achieve multifunctional properties, SMP nanocomposites reinforced by various nano-sized functional fillers could exhibit new properties that are significantly different from their pristine

counterparts and are particularly powerful for performance improvement and multi-responsive shape memory effect (SME) in the SMPs [3]. The SME can be controlled by incorporating nano-sized fillers into polymer matrix not only triggered by heat but also by light, electricity, magnetic field, mechanical force or infrared radiation individually, collectively and collaboratively [11].

It would be even more attractive if we could use two independent, abundantly available materials to produce SMEs of their nanocomposites. This could add new switches to the existing framework for novel SMEs, and could provide pristine materials with new opportunities, as well as new materials for wide ranges of applications [3-5]. The use of functional nano-sized fillers for the SME has triggered renewed research interest in building multifunctional SMP materials [12]. As both structural and functional materials, these SMP nanocomposites exhibit great potentials for many applications which show improved sensing capability, actuating capability and self-healing capability.

2 NANO-REINFORCEMENT FOR MULTIFUNCTIONAL SMP NANOCOMPOSITE

In the last decade, much effort has been made to introduce electromagnetic conductive fillers into the SMPs through electrically resistive joule heating. In this manner, external temperature heating, which is unfavorable for many applications but conventionally used to stimulate SMPs, can be avoided [13]. This section focuses on the progress of SMP nanocomposites triggered by the electrically resistive heating through incorporating conductive nano-sized fillers, including carbon-based nanofiller, metallic nanofiller and carbon nanopaper. Furthermore, the structure design and working mechanisms of electro-conductive SMP nanocomposites are also summarized and discussed.

There are several novel approaches to fabricate the electrically conductive SMP nanocomposites, including crosslinking between polymer macromolecules and CNTs, grafting CNTs onto the macromolecules, aligning CNTs in the polymer matrix into a chain or a continuous conductive network, synergy of CNTs and other types of conductive fillers etc [14-22]. These approaches help to improve the electrical actuation and significantly enable the SMP nanocomposites to meet the requirement in the practical applications. It should be noted that the effect of CNF on the electrical properties of the SMP nanocomposites is similar to that of CNTs. Sometimes, the CNF plays a more positive effect on the polymer matrix in improving the electrical performance due to the larger axis-length ratio [14]. However, the applications of the CNT and CNF are limited due to their high cost compared with carbon black in practical. An SMP nanocomposite incorporated with electrically conductive carbon black has been investigated, where the diameter of the carbon black is ~ 30 nm. Experimental results revealed that thermal conductivity and storage modulus of SMP nanocomposites have been significantly improved by adding the carbon black [14]. Furthermore, this type of SMP nanocomposites has excellent electrical conductivity with a percolation threshold ranged from approximately 3.0-5.0% in volume fraction. When an electric voltage of 30 V was applied, the shape recovery process of the tested SMP nanocomposite filled with 10 vol% carbon black was completed in ~ 100 s. Additionally, electrically conductive carbon black has also been introduced to the polyurethane-based SMP in order to actuate it by electricity, where the maximum concentration is about 30 wt% [14].

By forming conductive Ni chains under a weak static magnetic field (0.03 T), the electrical conductivity of the polyurethane SMP nanocomposite along the chain direction can be significantly improved [15]. This approach has been demonstrated to be more suitable for Joule heat induced shape recovery in comparison with that with randomly dispersed Ni nanoparticles. Scanning electronic microscopy (SEM) images reveal that Ni chains start to form at a volume fraction of 1%. With an increase in Ni content, eventually no clear Ni chain can be recognized and a continuous conductive network is formed. Results showed that the electrical resistivity of the SMP nanocomposites along the chain direction was always the lowest. For example, at a 10% volume fraction of Ni particles, electrical resistivity of the SMP nanocomposite filled with randomly dispersed Ni was $2.36 \times 10^4 \Omega\text{-cm}$, while that of the chained sample was $2.93 \times 10^6 \Omega\text{-cm}$ in the transverse direction and only $12.18 \Omega\text{-cm}$ along the chain direction. The Ni chains filled nanocomposite (with dimensions of $16 \times 0.6 \times 5 \text{ mm}^3$) can be electrically induced and heated from room temperature to 55°C upon an electric voltage of 6 V [15]. Inspired by this approach, the electrically aligned CNT chain has also been explored [16]. It was found that the aligned CNT chains could serve as long-distance conductive channels to bridge the carbon

black aggregations, and the electrical resistivity in those with chained CNTs was reduced for more than 100 times in comparison with that of SMP nanocomposites with randomly filled CNTs, resulting in the electrically responsive time significantly shortened as shown in Figure 1 [16].

Figure 1: Snap shots of shape recovery and temperature distributions. Sample A: SMP/CB, Sample B: SMP/CB/CNT (random), Sample C: SMP/CB/CNT (chained). Right figure shows the sample dimension and experimental setup for Sample C. Reproduced from Reference [16], Copyright 2011, AIP Publishing LLC.

Traditionally, electrically conductive fillers generate heat according to Joule's law and eventually facilitate the heat transfer to the SMP matrix and trigger the shape recovery. However, for the fabrication of electrically induced SMP nanocomposites, most of reported work is focused on conductive fillers embedded into the pristine polymer matrix. However, the resulting nanocomposites could not achieve a high electrical conductivity and a good performance to meet practical requirements. A higher loading level of filler is often required and a high viscosity of the mixture will be therefore resulted due to strong interactions between the filler and SMPs. This will prevent an efficient transfer of the properties of the filler to the matrix, and also make it difficult to achieve a uniform dispersion, especial for nano-sized filler due to their large surface area to aggregate [17-22]. Hence this approach is not a best choice to improve the electrical properties of polymer matrix. With respect to this issue, an attractive technique of making conductive nano-sized particles into various forms of film or paper has been introduced for the electrical actuation of SMP nanocomposites [17]. Currently, nanopaper enabled SMP nanocomposites have been systemically studied to promote the progress of electrical actuation. The nanocomposites were fabricated by coating the nanopapers onto the surface of SMP sheets by resin transfer modeling technique [17]. Generally the nanopaper is made from CNTs or CNFs. As the weight of each CNT nanopaper was increased from 0.6 g to 1.8 g, the average electrical resistivity of the composite samples was typically decreased from 4.877 to 0.937 $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ [18,19]. The more CNTs involved, the more conductive paths are formed in the nanopaper, therefore, the electrical current amplitude and electrical conductivity increases owing to that more electrons are forced to pass through the cross section of the bulk. To further improve the electrically induced performance and behavior of an SMP nanocomposite using the carbon nanopaper, a synergistic effect of carbon nanopaper and CNF was exploited for the electrical actuation [18]. The nanopaper was used to improve the electrical properties and achieve the actuation using electrical resistive heating for the SMP nanocomposites [20]. On the other hand, CNFs were blended into the SMP resin to facilitate the heat transfer from the nanopaper to the underlying SMP nanocomposite. Furthermore, the synergistic effect of carbon nanopaper and vertically aligned CNT was studied to mitigate the negative effect of randomly dispersed CNFs on the recovery ratio of SMP nanocomposites [20]. The combination of the nanopaper and magnetic alignment was also demonstrated to improve both electrical and thermal conductivities of SMP matrix and effectively accelerate the electro-active recovery behavior as shown in Figure 2 [21,22]. The vertical alignments directed the electric current to pass through the insulating polymer, and result showed that the nanopaper enabled SMP nanocomposite blended with 8 wt% vertically aligned nickel nanostrands successfully demonstrated the electrically triggered actuation [22]. Upon applying a constant voltage of 25 V, the deformed nanocomposite completes the shape recovery within 75 s. The SMP nanocomposite showed a 100% recovery ratio owing to the synergistic effect of nanopaper and magnetically aligned nano-sized filler [22].

Figure 2: Electrically resistive heating-induced SME of SMP/nanopaper nanocomposites with 8 wt% vertically aligned nickel nanostrands. Reproduced from Reference [22], Copyright 2011, RSC Publishing.

In brief, adding different electronically conductive components into a thermally responsive SMP could achieve shape recovery driven Joule heating. Such a composite can be used in electronic communication, MEMS and electromagnetic field, etc. For example, nanotube-filled polymers could be used for transparent conductive coatings, electrostatic dissipation, electrostatic painting, electromagnetic interference shielding, etc.

Nanocomposites of conjugated SMPs and functional nano-sized fillers are found to have multifunctional performance in optical, electrical, magnetic and other functional properties relative to conventional matrix [23]. One of the most popular applications for the SMP nanocomposites is sensors, such as gas sensors, electrochemical sensors, biosensors etc [24]. As the SMPs are the actuating materials, the SMP nanocomposites are therefore well used for the multifunctional materials with sensing and actuating capabilities. In the following section, SMP nanocomposites will be discussed for their sensing capability that is conjugated with the internal actuating capability from SMP for multifunctionalization.

SMP materials are demonstrated to have both SME and temperature memory effect (TME). Therefore, it is critical to record and monitor their shape and temperature change in the recovery process. A SMP made from a cross-linked poly(cyclooctene) matrix and a chromogenic oligo(*p*-phenylene vinylene) dye has been used to detect the temperature change [24]. The dye concentration was chosen to allow for self-assembly upon drying, resulting in the formation of excimers. Exposure of the dye above the melting transition temperature of the matrix leads to the dye molecules to dissolution and results in a pronounced change of their absorption and fluorescence color. The optical changes are reversible; i.e., the aggregate absorption and emission are restored upon cooling back below the melting transition temperature. Thus the sensing ability allows the SMP to monitor the set/release temperatures through color change.

Another strategy to achieve the multifunctional sensing and actuating capabilities is making the electrically conductive SMP nanocomposites [23,24]. The electrical property enables the nanocomposites to respond to the changes in temperature and shape (or strain) through detecting their electrical resistivity. The nano-sized carbon black and chopped short carbon fiber were initially introduced to integrate into the SMP matrix with sensing and actuating capabilities [23]. Experimental results revealed that the electrical resistance of the SMP nanocomposites decreased with temperature increased [23]. However, the electrical resistance reaches its peak value approximate at 85°C, and then it gets smaller value till to 100°C, resulting in the nanocomposites showing a classical negative temperature coefficient effect. On the other hand, the relationship between electrical resistance as a function of strain of the SMP nanocomposites was studied [23]. It was found that the electrical resistance increased continuously with an increase in the strain from 0 to 3% under a uniaxial stretch force [23]. The electrical properties of the SMP nanocomposites responded sensitively to the strain changes. With the increase of strain, the distance of the conductive paths is enlarged, resulting in the increase of electrical resistance by several orders upon stretching. These are contributed to destruction of the structure of the electrically conductive paths or network [25].

Besides the sensing capability to temperature and strain, the surface coating of nanopaper on the SMP nanocomposites have also been demonstrated to have sensing capability of detecting variation of water contents in tested samples [24]. Nanopaper made from CNT or CNF is of a porous structure and

expected to be suitable for fire protection and lightning strike protection. Therefore the study on the electrically sensing response to water content is essential for the potential applications of nanopaper enabled SMP nanocomposites [24]. Experimental results showed that the electrical resistivity of the nanopapers with 0.6 g, 1.2 g, 1.8 g and 2.4 g of multi-walled CNTs was increased with an increase of the water content. However, the effect of water content on the electrical resistivity is not clear when the relative water concentration is low. It is expected that the water molecules behave like electron donors and have a theoretical effect on the dielectric constant of multi-walled CNTs in the nanopaper.

In the SMP nanocomposites, the electrically conductive components enable them with sensing capability, whereas the SMP matrix is the actuating component originated from output recovery force in the shape recovery process. The SMP nanocomposites have been demonstrated as actuators, although their output recovery strength is relative low. When the 2.4 g multi-walled CNT nanopaper was incorporated with the SMP matrix, a 5-gram mass was actuated and driven up from 0 to 30 mm in height as shown in Figure 3. In this type of SMP nanocomposite, the multifunctionalization has been achieved by integrating with sensing and actuating capabilities. On the other hand, the polystyrene SMP nanocomposite incorporated with short carbon fibers and carbon black showed the sensing response to changes in temperature and strain in the tested sample [23]. The capability has been demonstrated to actuate the motion of the table tennis ball [23]. Smart devices and structures utilizing this exciting nanocomposite are currently being developed, which could have great potentials in application encompassing sensors and actuators.

Figure 3: Series of photographs showing the electro-activate shape memory effect of SMP/nanopaper nanocomposite and actuating the motion of 5-gram mass. The permanent shape is a plane stripe of nanocomposite and the temporary shape is deformed as a right-angled shape. Reproduced from Reference [24], Copyright 2011, Elsevier.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Significant advances have been made over the past few years in design, characterisation, simulation and potential application of the SMP nanocomposite to enhance their mechanical, thermal, optical, electrical and magnetic properties. A number of design methodologies, prototypes and initial trials have been proposed and discussed, but many conflicting issues remain to be resolved. Actuation approaches, multifunctionalization and application pose special requirements to most of properties of SMP nanocomposites, of which the mechanical enhancement and triggering optimization are essential and critical. For biomedical applications, challenges exist with non-contact and actuation approach, the incorporation of the SME to fulfil the multi-dimensional requirements of the modulus, triggering/fixing conditions, control of degree and rate of fixing/recovery, magnitude of recovery force, biocompatibility and rate of biodegradability, etc. The other key issue may lie in the control of the SME inside the human body, where the material must interact with complicated chemical environments, such as acids, salts and alkali. For engineering structures, the low recovery strength and the fact that the SMP materials become too soft above their transition temperatures still remain major concerns that are well known but difficult to avoid. Proper or even novel approaches should be explored to solve these issues to effectively enhance the mechanical performance and output recovery strength of SMP nanocomposites above their transition temperatures. With respect to these above mentioned issues, actuation approaches and multifunctionalization of nanocomposites play essential

and critical roles in the research and development of SMP materials. The existing problems could be overcome by finding more innovative applications that exploit the existing features and capacities of SMPs and their nanocomposites. These objectives require tremendous creativity and smart visions as well as great investment.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been financially supported by National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 51103032), the special funding of China Postdoctoral Science Foundation (2012T50328), Program for New Century Excellent Talents in University (Grant No. NCET-13-0172) and A Foundation for the Author of National Excellent Doctoral Dissertation of PR China (Grant No. 201328).

REFERENCES

- [1] H. B. Lu and J. H. Gou, Study on 3-D high conductive graphene buckypaper for electrical actuation of shape memory polymer, *Nanoscience and Nanotechnology Letters*, **4**, 2012, pp. 1155-1159. (doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1166/nnl.2012.1455>).
- [2] T. Xie, Tunable polymer multi-shape memory effect, *Nature*, **464**, 2010, pp. 267-270. (doi: [10.1038/nature08863](http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/nature08863)).
- [3] C. C. Wang, W. M. Huang, Z. Ding, Y. Zhao, and H. Purnawali, Cooling-/water-responsive shape memory hybrids, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 1178-1182. (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.03.027](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2012.03.027)).
- [4] H. B. Lu, P. P. Bai, W. L. Yin and W. M. Huang, Magnetically aligned carbon nanotubes in nanopaper for electro-activated shape-memory nanocomposites, *Nanoscience and Nanotechnology Letters*, **5**, 2013, pp. 732-736. (doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1166/nnl.2013.1611>).
- [5] Q. Meng and J. Hu, A review of shape memory polymer composites and blends, *Composites. Part A-Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **40**, 2009, pp. 1661-1672. (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2009.08.011](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2009.08.011)).
- [6] W. M. Huang, Z. Ding, C. C. Wang, J. Wei, Y. Zhao and H. Purnawali, Shape memory materials, *Materials Today*, **13**, 2010, pp. 54-61. (doi: [10.1016/S1369-7021\(10\)70128-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S1369-7021(10)70128-0)).
- [7] I. A. Rousseau, Challenges of shape memory polymers: A review of the progress toward overcoming SMP's limitations, *Polymer Engineering & Science*, **48**, 2008, pp. 2075-2089. (doi: [10.1002/pen.21213](http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/pen.21213)).
- [8] K. Gall, M. Mikulas, N. A. Munshi, F. Beavers and M. Tupper, Carbon fiber reinforced shape memory polymer composites, *Journal of Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, **11**, 2000, pp. 877-886. (doi: [10.1106/EJGR-EWNM-6CLX-3X2M](http://dx.doi.org/10.1106/EJGR-EWNM-6CLX-3X2M)).
- [9] F. Hussain, M. Hojjati and M. Okamoto, Review article: polymer-matrix nanocomposites, processing, manufacturing, and application: an overview, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **40**, 2006, pp. 1511-1575. (doi: [10.1177/0021998306067321](http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0021998306067321)).
- [10] I. V. Khudyakov, R. D. Zopf and N. J. Turro, Polyurethane nanocomposites, *Designed Monomers and Polymers*, **12**, 2009, pp. 279-290. (doi: [10.1163/156855509X448253](http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/156855509X448253)).
- [11] J. S. Leng and S. Y. Du, Shape-memory polymers and multifunctional composites, Vol. 6, CRC Press LLC, 2010.
- [12] M. Behl, M. Y. Razzaq and A. Lendlein, Multifunctional shape-memory polymers, *Advanced Materials*, **22**, 2010, pp. 3388-3410. (doi: [10.1002/adma.200904447](http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/adma.200904447)).
- [13] Y. J. Liu, H. B. Lv, X. Lan, J. S. Leng and S. Y. Du, Review of electro-activate shape-memory polymer composite, *Composites Science and Technology*, **69**, 2009, pp. 2064-2068. (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.08.016](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.08.016)).
- [14] J. S. Leng, X. Lan, Y. J. Liu and S. Y. Du, Electroactive thermoset shape memory polymer nanocomposite filled with nanocarbon powders, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **18**, 2009, p. 074003. (doi: [10.1088/0964-1726/18/7/074003](http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/18/7/074003)).

- [15] J. S. Leng, X. Lan, Y. J. Liu and S. Y. Du, Electrical conductivity of thermoresponsive shape-memory polymer with embedded micron sized Ni powder chains, *Applied Physics Letters*, **92**, 2008, p. 014104. (doi: [10.1063/1.2829388](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2829388)).
- [16] K. Yu, Z. Zhang, Y. J. Liu, and J. S. Leng, Carbon nanotube chains in a shape memory polymer/carbon black composite: to significantly reduce the electrical resistivity, *Applied Physics Letters*, **98**, 2011, p. 074102. (doi: [10.1063/1.3556621](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3556621)).
- [17] H. B. Lu, F. Liang, Y. T. Yao, J. H. Gou and D Hui, Self-assembled multi-layered carbon nanofiber nanopaper for significantly improving electrical actuation of shape memory polymer nanocomposite, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **59**, 2014, pp. 191-195. (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesb.2013.12.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2013.12.009)).
- [18] H. B. Lu, Y. J. Liu, J. H. Gou, J. S. Leng and S. Y. Du, Electrical properties and shape-memory behavior of self-assembled carbon nanofiber nanopaper incorporated with shape-memory polymer, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **19**, 2010, p. 075021. (doi: [10.1088/0964-1726/19/7/075021](https://doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/19/7/075021)).
- [19] H. B. Lu and J. H. Gou, Fabrication and electroactivate responsive behavior of shape-memory nanocomposite incorporated with self-assembled multi-walled carbon nanotube nanopaper, *Polymers for Advanced Technologies*, **23**, 2012, pp. 1529-1535. (doi: [10.1002/pat.2074](https://doi.org/10.1002/pat.2074)).
- [20] H. B. Lu, Y. J. Liu, J. H. Gou, J. S. Leng and S. Y. Du, Synergistic effect of carbon nanofiber and carbon nanopaper on shape memory polymer composite, *Applied Physics Letters*, **96**, 2010, p. 084102. (doi: [10.1063/1.3323096](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3323096)).
- [21] H. B. Lu, J. H. Gou, J. S. Leng and S. Y. Du, Magnetically aligned carbon nanotube in nanopaper enabled shape-memory nanocomposite for high speed electrical actuation, *Applied Physics Letters*, **98**, 2011, p. 174105. (doi: [10.1063/1.3585669](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3585669)).
- [22] H. B. Lu, F. Liang and J. H. Gou, Nanopaper Enabled Shape-Memory Nanocomposite with Vertically Aligned Nickel Nanostrand: Controlled Synthesis and Electrical Actuation, *Soft Matter*, **7**, 2011, pp. 7416-7423. (doi: [10.1039/C1SM05765K](https://doi.org/10.1039/C1SM05765K)).
- [23] H. B. Lu, K. Yu, Y. J. Liu and J. S. Leng, Sensing and actuating capabilities of a shape memory polymer composite integrated with hybrid filler, *Smart Materials and Structures*, **19**, 2010, p. 065014. (doi: [10.1088/0964-1726/19/6/065014](https://doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/19/6/065014)).
- [24] H. B. Lu, Y. J. Liu, J. Gou, J. S. Leng and S. Y. Du, Surface coating of multi-walled carbon nanotube nanopaper on shape-memory polymer for multifunctionalization, *Composites Science and Technology*, **71**, 2011, pp. 1427-1434. (doi: [10.1016/j.compscitech.2011.05.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2011.05.016)).